

Title: The Roles of Big Data in Building Performance: A Function of Relationships and Contexts

Abstract

This study investigates how big data contributes to performance in organizations. This study employed an integrative literature review method to construct knowledge about performance in organizations concerning the use of big data and the implementation of big data analytics. This article synthesized knowledge about how big data enhances performance. This article establishes that performance is the quality of functioning that is a key determinant of organizational success or failure. Based on the findings from the synthesized literature, this article proposes that performance is a function of relationships and contexts. Essentially, the relationship between big data, big data analytics, and requisite big data analytics capabilities that include level of knowledge, level of skills, sensing, seizing, transforming, tangible resources, and intangible resources is crucial in building various types of performance and there are varying contextual factors regulating the relationships. Big data on its own is not sufficient in bringing about the desired performance, but a combination of processes for storing, acquiring, processing, analyzing, and interpreting big data in conjunction with the competencies or resources for big data analytics is required. This article emphasizes that the big data-performance connection is dependent on big data analytics processes, requisite big data analytics capabilities, the generation of valuable insights or knowledge, the capacity for data and analytics to enhance decision-making, and the creation of value and competitive advantage through insight-backed decision-making. In addition, this article highlights further research problems for the research community to address and provides useful recommendations for implementation by practitioners.

Keywords: big data, big data analytics, big data analytics capabilities, competitive advantage, contexts, decision-making, insight, knowledge, organizational performance

Introduction

The exponential developments and ubiquity of technologies which include sensor networks, cyber-physical systems, and Internet of Things (IoT) have increased the collection of data on an enormous scale in many

domains such as health care, social media, smart cities, agriculture, finance, education, manufacturing, etc., (Hariri, Fredericks, & Bowers, 2019). Organizations can now access a vast amount of data which includes clickstream data (e.g., web and social media content like tweets, blogs, and Facebook postings), transaction data such as structured data from retail transactions, customer profiles, video data from retail and stores, and voice data such as data from phone calls, call centers, and customer service (Akter, 2016). Corporations generate and can acquire multiple types of data that are unstructured, voluminous and of high speed such as SMS texts, CCTV, RFID, barcode scanner, geographic information systems (GIS), Instagram pictures, call centre logs, client chats, click stream on the web, social media such as Facebook, Blogs, YouTube, Genomics, Internet of Things, etc., (Moorthy, 2015). Essentially, data is information that exists in a specified format and follows a set of closed patterns and is used according to requirements (Gupta, Drave, Dwivedi, & Baabdullah, 2020). Data is regarded as the next most crucial factor after labor and land. Moreover, big data is complex and difficult to handle and decode (Gupta et al., 2020), which creates the need for sophisticated data analysis and management, i.e., big data analytics (BDA). BDA is the strategy for analyzing large volumes of data or big data, which is collected through a variety of sources, such as images, sensors, videos, social media contents, sales transaction entries, and many others” (Shahbaz et al., 2020, p. 1). The pace of adoption of big data analytics (BDA) is increasing due to its prospects and potential advantages (Lutfi et al., 2022).

Literature suggests that big data analytics can create business value. There is growing interest in literature about the value that organizations can derive from using big data analytics towards attaining organizational goals (Mikalef, Boura, Lekakos, & Krogstie, 2019). Big data system quality accounts for 74% of the variance in BDA business value (Ji-fan Ren, Fosso Wamba, Akter, Dubey, & Childe, 2016). An organization’s analytics culture has a strong positive effect on strategic business value (Fosso Wamba, Queiroz, Wu, & Sivarajah, 2020). BDA adds value which results in organizational success (Mushore & Kyobe, 2022). Still, organizations face numerous challenges when attempting to generate value from their big data analytics (Mikalef et al., 2019).

Literature has confirmed that BDA improves performance, but little is known about how firms translate their BDA into performance. For instance, big data analytics has a significant relationship with organizational performance (S. Ali & Xie, 2021). The application of BDA accounted for 34% variance in organizational performance (Shabbir & Gardezi, 2020). Big data is acclaimed as the latest sophisticated thing that provides improved efficiency, effectiveness, innovativeness, and competitive advantage to firms (Suoniemi, Meyer-Waarden, & Munzel, 2017). The utilization of BDA provides performance benefits that include reduction in operating cost or production time, improvement of customer service, and customer satisfaction with firms' product quality (Popovic, Hackney, Tassabehji, & Castelli, 2016). Organizations can take advantage of big data and big data analytics in improving their performance (D. Q. Chen, Preston, & Swink, 2015). Thus, how can performance gains be achieved from big data? How do organizations effectively leverage big data analytics towards specific business outcomes? Therefore, this study answers the research question about how big data contributes to performance.

Method

This study followed the guidelines for writing integrative literature reviews described by Torraco (2016). Literature review is a means of answering specific research questions about a topic (Torraco, 2016). This article answers the research question about how big data influences performance. This research question serves as the boundary for the literature to be reviewed and issues to be examined in this study.

Torraco (2016) stated that literature review involves reviewing and synthesizing literature about a topic, which is a creative act that results in the generation of new knowledge about the topic being explored. This study synthesized new knowledge about big data and performance by weaving together ideas found in extant literature into a new model.

Identification of Publications

This search for publications that are relevant to the research questions was conducted between May 2023 and October 2025. To identify relevant publications, several literature databases were examined, namely

Google Scholar, Wiley online, Taylor and Francis Online, Springer Link, Science Direct, Sage Journals, Emerald Insight, Paperity, and CORE. The keywords employed for the search were big data AND performance, big data analytics AND performance, big data analytics capabilities AND performance, big data OR big data analytics OR big data analytics capabilities AND performance.

Literature Screening and Selection

The literature screening process involves using publication titles and abstracts for initial screening of publications. Publications with titles that were aligned with the subject under investigation were retrieved from the databases. The abstracts of the retrieved publications were examined, the text and the methodology used were examined. Some publications were eliminated from the review based on the type of methodology employed. Book chapters, literature reviews, and some conceptual papers were eliminated. Publications that conducted empirical testing and qualitative research that employed case study and interview methods were included. Appendix A (figure two) portrays the publication selection process.

The quality of the publications retrieved from the databases was evaluated through a screening process that involved using an inclusion and exclusion criteria. The publications included were those that examined big data or big data analytics or big data analytics capabilities and performance such as firm performance, operational performance, etc., the impacts of big data analytics on organizational value and business value, and articles that indicate that the study population is using big data in their operations or processes. The publications excluded were those that examined big data analytics projects evaluation, big data processing software or technologies, big data applications in various industries, big data and smart cities, big data storage, cloud computing and big data, high-performance computing and big data analytics, big data and computer architectures, big data architecture, behavior analysis and big data, big data application for e-governance, articles addressing the performance of big data analytics frameworks and technologies such as Spark, Flink, Apache, etc., big data analytics publications that addressed performance of machine learning, cybersecurity, cloud computing platforms, object stores, big data infrastructure performance, etc., Fifty three publications that were relevant to the reviewed topic were included based on the screening process.

During the review, a backward process suggested by Webster and Watson (2002) was used in identifying more publications, the citations in the reviewed publications provided leads in generating more relevant literature, and five publications were included based on the process. In addition, the search for publications about significant theories and concepts from databases for peer reviewed publications and web-based databases yielded five more literature which were also included in the integrative literature review.

Analysis and Synthesis

The findings from the selected publications were extracted and summarized. The summarized findings were analyzed to identify central ideas and patterns from the reviewed literature. The summarized findings were synthesized using a concept-centric approach suggested by Webster & Watson (2002). The synthesis involves grouping and discussing the concepts identified. The concepts provided the organizing framework for the review. The ideas were synthesized to create new knowledge about big data's connection with performance. This is aligned with Torraco's (2016) suggestions that one of the goals of a literature review is synthesis, i.e., creating something basically new or developing new ways of thinking about a topic.

Theoretical Development

A guiding theory provides the foundation for a coherent conceptual structuring while a variance process is valuable for building a conceptual model (Webster & Watson, 2002). Thus, this article used the Theory of Performance (Elger, 2007) and the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece et al 1997; Teece, 2007) as the guiding theories and developed the conceptual model by following the ideas from the variance process which entails mapping the identified independent variables or concepts (e.g., big data) that produced variation on the dependent variables or concepts (performance). Furthermore, the justification of the conceptual model was made through propositions. Three propositions were developed to convey the relationships between the variables to reveal an in-depth understanding of the big data-performance connection. The logical reasoning (why) behind the relationships between the variables of the big data-performance connection provided the justification for the theory development.

The Conceptual Framework for the Big Data-Performance Connection

There is an increasing tendency globally for organizations to apply BDA instead of depending on intuition for effective decision-making. Leaders are increasingly making decisions based on real-time insights generated from big data (Yasmin, Tatoglu, Selcukkili, Zaim, & Delen, 2020; Mikalef et al., 2019). Big data has changed the course of business management from human-centricity (making decisions based on intuitions) to data-centricity which involves making decision by using data for pattern identification, predictions, and assessment of achievement and outcomes (Moorthy, 2015). Firms generate knowledge from BDA to facilitate precise, quicker, and efficient decision-making (Gul & Al-Faryan, 2023). Organizations use big data analytics to convert data into insights and business intelligence (developing a deep understanding of market needs and generating new and unique insights for business development) needed at various levels in the organization (C-H. Chen, 2023). Big data is one of the widely used technologies or services that enable businesses to develop and maintain a competitive advantage (Lutfi et al., 2022). Big data analytics positively influence organizational competitive advantage, business growth, and asset productivity, such as asset turnover rate and profitability (D. Q. Chen et al., 2015). The application of BDA has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance (Shabbir & Gardezi, 2020). Big data analytics capabilities support organizations in making intelligent business decisions that contribute to enhanced company performance and sustainability (Arshad, Yu, Qadir, Ahmad, & Rafique, 2022). Big data analytics skills, which include human resource skills and knowledge (e.g., skills in math, programming, business knowledge, etc.), are useful in deriving market insights from big data in improving firms' performance (Suoniemi et al., 2017). BDA management capabilities and BDA technology capabilities along with infrastructure and value attributes of the business models generated growth and improved financial performance (Song et al., 2022). Thus, this article established that there is an association between big data and performance via data-driven insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage.

Performance is the quality of functioning or the extent of the success of an entity or process. Performance is the action or process of accomplishing a task, function, or duty. It is how well a task, function, or duty is executed (American Psychological Association [APA], 2018). At the same time, there are various types of

tasks within a firm, and the performance of these tasks may lead to various levels of performance within the organization or overall firm/organizational performance. Performance may be described as a specific level of achievement, particular ability, or other attributes. Performance denotes the achievement of goals and objectives (APA, 2018).

The findings from literature indicate that firms' goals are diverse which implies that there are different types of performance associated with a firm. While an organization's performance signifies its values, vision, and mission. For instance, some of the performance associated with big data include environmental performance, innovative performance, supply chain performance, market performance, etc., which are indications of the firm's mission, vision, and values.

The Theory of Performance (ToP) indicates that performance means producing valued results through an individual, group, or organization's collaborative efforts (Elger, 2007). Performance is the valuable result that comes from taking a series of actions by integrating skills and knowledge (Elger, 2007). Based on the assumptions from the theory of performance, this article suggests that performance is an outcome. Performance is an outcome that is a product of many variables. The variables include actions or decision making, knowledge or capabilities, etc., thus, *performance comes from actions or decision making that is based on insights generated by integrating big data analytics capabilities into the analysis of big data.*

The theory of performance emphasizes that performance depends holistically on five varying factors which are level of knowledge, levels of skills, level of identity, contexts, personal factors, and fixed factors. Similarly, this article suggests that performance in the era of big data depends on these factors. Knowledge refers to concepts, information, theories, and principles. Skills refer to the breadth of application or effectiveness in doing something. Contexts are the variables associated with the situation in which an organization operates. (Elger, 2007). Based on the reviewed literature about big data and performance, this article established that the aforementioned assumptions from the theory of performance about level of knowledge, level of skills, and contexts are all encapsulated under the big data analytics capabilities and are important factors that contribute to performance in the big data era. Specifically, Gupta and George's (2016) BDAC framework indicates that a firm's capability to successfully orchestrate big data analytics for

performance gains is based on its tangible resources (e.g., data, big data technologies, infrastructure, and financial resources), human skills (technical and business analytics skills), and intangible resources such as data-driven culture and organization learning. Concurrently, this article suggests that the level of knowledge and level of skills' assumptions from the theory of performance are relevant elements that contribute to performance and are part of the BDAC framework under the human resource skills construct. For instance, BDA capabilities that include people's expertise, analytical capabilities, and organizational factors such as employee engagement and top management support, enhance decision-making and high value business performance in manufacturing firms (Popovic et al., 2016). BDA results in high performance in conditions where there is an adequate level of fit or alignment between task, technology, people, and structures (Mushore & Kyobe, 2022).

Personal and fixed factors are components relating to the individual, e.g., situation and genetics. This article suggests that these are the characteristics embodied in an organization's human resources. This article proposes that personal and fixed factors have a crucial relationship with workers' level of knowledge and skills. Holistically, personal and fixed factors, knowledge, and skills are important elements of an organization's human resource capabilities. These elements play crucial roles in an organization's performance. They are unique to an organization and are important determinants of an organization's performance.

The significance of the elements drawn from the Theory of Performance in relation to performance in the age of big data can be expounded further through the lens of the Dynamic Capabilities Theory. A firm's successful adaptation to changing business environment depends on its ability to integrate internal and external competencies (Teece et al., 1997). Thus, the internal competencies are essentially the employees' knowledge and skills which are influenced by the personal and fixed factors. Moreover, internal competencies possessed by the workers are relevant for sensing, seizing, and transforming, which are the further extensions of the assumptions of the Dynamic Capabilities Theory suggested by Teece, (2007). Sensing entails the identification and assessments of threats and opportunities. Seizing involves making decisions about opportunities and taking actions. Transforming revolves around the reconfiguration of

resources and capabilities towards sustainable competitiveness. Therefore, based on the assumptions from the Dynamic Capabilities theory, this article advocates that workplace performance depends on the competencies of the employees and emphasizes that the internal competencies, i.e., employees' capabilities for performing sensing, seizing, and transforming are relevant facets of Big Data Analytics Capabilities which are essential in driving workplace performance in order to maintain competitiveness.

In addition, the theory of performance specifies that the drivers of effective performance include an enriching environment and people's mindsets (setting challenging goals, intrinsic motivation, etc.), and immersion in a positive environment (enabling psychological safety), and engaging reflective practices which include feedback, developmental processes, and assessment (Elger, 2007). Similarly, this particular assumption from the theory of performance may also be accounted for under the intangible resource constructs of Gupta and George's (2016) BDAC framework, which consist of culture, organization learning, etc.,

Thus, based on assumptions drawn from the theory of performance in conjunction with the dynamic capabilities theory and the evidence from the reviewed literature regarding the generation of insights from big data through big data analytics and data-driven decision-making and ensuing competitive advantage, this article presents a theoretical statement that provides a coherent description of how big data leads to performance. *The big data-performance connection posits that performance is a function of the BDAC that encompasses knowledge, skills (managerial, business, & technical), sensing, seizing, transformation, and tangible and intangible resources integrated into big data analytics for the generation of insights from big data under varying conditions (environment) or contexts, which can be incorporated into decision-making that engenders competitive advantage.* The following sections covers the discussion about the delineation of the big data constructs and the relationships between the constructs and organizational performance while some contextual factors' roles in the big-data performance connection are herewith outlined.

The Big Data Constructs

Big Data

The exponential improvements in digital technologies in the era of digitalization make digital technologies an integral part of life, business, communication, and information exchanges, resulting in the continuous generation of the massive volume of data regarded as big data (Ditkaew & Suttipun, 2023). Big data are datasets that appear in exabytes (EB), petabytes, zetabytes (ZB), and their characteristics include volume, velocity, variety, veracity, and value (Hariri et al., 2019). Volume refers to the size and scale of the datasets. Variety refers to the forms of data in a dataset, which are structured data (well-organized and easily sorted), semi-structured data, and unstructured data such as text and multimedia content. Velocity is the speed of production or the speed of processing, e.g., real-time, streaming, etc., Veracity is the quality of the data; good, bad, and undefined. For instance, data can be inconsistent, noisy, ambiguous, uncertain, incomplete, or imprecise. Value entails the context and usefulness of data in decision-making (Hariri et al., 2019). Big data is a variety of digital data sets that is made possible by advancements in computing power and which is analyzed using algorithms.

Big Data Analytics

The emergence of big data analytics (BDA) stems from the increasing enormity and complexity of data generated due to digital transformation and technological trends such as connected devices, machines, wearables, sensors, web-based/online media platforms, etc. (Niebel, Rasel, & Viète, 2019). BDA refers to “an integrated data collection and analysis process that provide solid insights for managerial decision-making” (Akter, Wamba, Barret, & Biswas, 2018). BDA is the process of collecting, examining, and analyzing large amounts of data to discover market trends, insights, and patterns that can help companies make better decisions. Analytics are all the activities that transform data into action (Ohman, Arvidsson, Jonsson, & Kaipia, 2021). Data analytics is the set of techniques that is focused on gaining actionable insights in making smart decisions from a massive amount of data (Duan & Xu, 2021). Big data predictive analytics is the technique for unwinding voluminous data in a format that enables critical decision-making

for business operations (Gupta et al., 2020). Big data analytics help in generating insights that are useful in transforming business strategies, models, and business functions (D. Q. Chen et al., 2015). Big data analytics enable the capacity for identifying patterns and relationships in the internal and external business environment, which support and facilitate business processes, market forecasting, and accurate decision-making (Hautala-Kankaanpaa, 2023). Big data is a strategic resource valuable in the firm's value-creating processes with the possibilities for creating competitive advantage if leveraged by big data analytics capabilities (Suoniemi et al., 2017).

Big Data Analytics Capabilities

Big data analytics capabilities are crucial in delivering value from big data analytics. BDAC is defined as "a firm's ability to assemble, integrate, and deploy its big data-specific resources" (Gupta & George, 2016, p. 1049). Big data analytics capabilities refer to "the competence to provide business insights using data management, infrastructure (technology), and talent (personnel) capabilities to transform business into a competitive force" (Fosso Wamba et al., 2017). BDA capabilities, which are multi-dimensional, promote the ability to process, analyze, and visualize substantial amounts of structured and unstructured data (C-H. Chen, 2023). Big data analytics capability consists of three primary dimensions which are management capability, technology capability, and talent capability (Akter, 2016). BDAC entails dimensions such as tangible resources, e.g., data, technology, etc., human resources, e.g., technical and managerial skills, and intangible resources, e.g., organizational learning and data-driven culture in capturing and analyzing data to generate insights (Mikalef, Krigstie, Pappas, & Pavlou, 2020). Combining big data analytics capabilities such as technology capability, management capability, and personnel capability is essential in exploring data potential toward developing and gaining business insights (Fosso Wamba et al., 2020).

BDAC is about tools, technologies, people, leadership, governance, culture, methods, and processes for turning data into knowledge and integrating the knowledge within the firm (Ohman et al., 2021). BDA technologies and tools enable businesses to generate valuable information from a large amount of digital data sets, and the data-generated information is important for firms operating in a dynamic, turbulent, and

highly competitive business environment (T. Karaboga, Zehir, Tatoglu, E. Karaboga, & Bouguerra, 2022). Big data analytics capability enables the conversion of data that a firm collects into business value by leveraging big data into actionable insights (Mikalef et al., 2019). Big data analytics capabilities lead to the utilization of data in enhancing the understanding of data-related opportunities and the creation of business value, growth, and new opportunities for the company (Hautala-Kankaanpaa, 2023).

The Performance Paradigms and their Relationship with Big Data

There are different types of performance associated with big data and big data analytics, for instance, the three-fold performance, which includes market, financial, and operational performance, is important for the long-term sustainability of an organization (Gupta et al., 2020). Performance can be construed as the achievement of organizational goals such as strengthening financial position, capturing a large share of the market, optimizing operations, and acquiring respectable margins and profits from sales and cost savings (Gupta et al., 2020). The various types of performance associated with big data, big data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities which are found in the reviewed literature are discussed in the following sections.

Big Data and Organizational Performance

Organizational performance entails the actual productivity or outcomes of an organization compared with the desired outcomes or objectives (Shabbir & Gardezi, 2020). Organizational performance involves satisfying shareholders' needs and organizational survival requirements through market share, best quality goods, customer retention, sales growth, profitability, and return on investment, etc. (S. Ali & Xie, 2021; S. Ali et al., 2020). BDA facilitates a large base of information that can be converted into usable knowledge for decision-making, which positively influences organizational performance (Marchena Sekli & De La Vega, 2021). Data analytics transform data into actionable insights for effective decision-making, which leads to improved or higher organizational performance (McCartney & Fu, 2022).

HR analytics that are developed based on robust AI platforms and analytic capabilities that allow the translation of data into meaningful insights support organizational evidence-based management and

ultimately leads to organizational performance (McCartney & Fu, 2022). Big data analytics such as predictive or prescriptive analytics, have a higher influence on organizational performance (Oesterreich, Antona, Teuteberga, & Dwivedi, 2022). BDA positively influences knowledge management processes such as knowledge acquisition, knowledge dissemination, and knowledge utilization, which positively influences organizational performance in higher educational institutions (Marchena Sekli & De La Vega, 2021). BDAC positively impacts operational performance, which results in increased organizational performance (Zhu, Du, Shahzad, & Wattoo, 2022). Strong BDAC supports strategies and guides decision-making and ultimately improves organizational performance (Shahzad, Du, Khan, & Wang, 2022).

Big Data and Firm Performance

The concept of firm performance has been used in literature when investigating organizational performance, wherein firm performance entails return on sales, product development, number of new products and services or projects, sales growth, and market share (Yasmin et al., 2020). Firm performance is the degree to which a firm has superior performance relative to its competition in the areas of operational excellence, customer relationship, and revenue growth (Rai, Patnayakuni, & Seth, 2006). Firm performance is the ability of a firm to gain and retain customers, improve sales, profitability, and return on investment. Firm performance improves with the adoption of BDA and combined with information sharing, which enables firms to effectively and efficiently perform their day-to-day duties to achieve their objectives (Lutfi et al., 2022). Big data analytics capability (BDAC) has a positive impact on firm performance (Aker, 2016). BDA social systems which are human factors (BDA skills, knowledge, and management capabilities) and organizational structure (data-driven culture and informational guidance) have a stronger influence in enhancing business performance (Oesterreich et al., 2022).

In the BDA environment, strategic analytic capabilities that include technology capability: analytics infrastructure such as networks and applications, and information capability, the ability to provide complete, accurate, and current information, have significant positive effects on firm performance (Aker et al., 2018). Technology capability cum information capability leads to improved firm performance

through talent capability which is a strategic analytic capability (Akter et al., 2018). Big data resources that include big data analytics, organizational resources, and technology resources have positive significant effect (37% variance) on marketing capabilities and consequently have positive effect on firm performance (Suoniemi et al., 2017).

BDA adoption has a strong, favourable, and positive impact on firm performance in the Jordanian hospitality industry (Lutfi et al., 2022). BDAC accounts for 21.52% of return on sales and 14.77% in sales growth (Yasmin et al., 2020). BDAC accounts for 18.41% of product development and 17.74% of a number of new products and services projects (Yasmin et al., 2020). BDA (advanced analytics) increases perceived sales performance in pharmaceutical organizations). Big data system quality, that includes system reliability, adaptability, integration, response time, accessibility, and privacy accounts for 70% of the variance in big data information quality and 76% of the variance in firm performance (Ji-fan Ren et al., 2016). BDA (BDA technical systems, predictive analytics, and prescriptive analytics) produces effects on firm performance (Oesterreich et al., 2022).

Big Data and Financial Performance

In a big data environment, BDA system quality and BDA information quality that encompasses accuracy, format, currency, and completeness are important in enhancing business value and firm's financial performance (Ji-fan Ren et al., 2016). Big data analytics positively influence the decision-making process and forecasting process, while accurate and quick decision-making and forecasting processes positively impact financial performance (Chatterjee, Chaudhuri, Gupta, Sivarajah, & Bag, 2023). Leveraging BDAC, such as management, technology, and talent capabilities impacts financial performance (Akter, 2016). BDA capabilities that include infrastructure (e.g., software applications), human resources (knowledge of applications and technical expertise), and management capabilities (strategy) are strongly related to financial performance (Yasmin et al., 2020). Big data predictive analytics capabilities that include managerial and technical skills positively impact the financial performance of organizations in various industries such as banking, insurance, manufacturing, technology, etc. (Gupta et al., 2020). Big data and

predictive analytics adoption have a positively significant relationship with economic performance in the food waste and recycling industry (Nilashi et al., 2023). Big data analytics management capability is positively and significantly associated with the effects of BDA on the financial performance of Turkish firms, according to a study of IT experts who actively use big data in their operations (T. Karaboga et al., 2022). Organizations' analytics culture and BDA-enabled sensing capabilities have a significant positive influence on financial performance (Fosso Wamba et al., 2020). Data-driven culture mediates the relationship between big data analytics management capability and the effects of BDA on firms' financial performance (T. Karaboga et al., 2022).

Big Data and Operational Performance

Operational performance is a firm's operational efficiency, which accounts for the firm's competitiveness and profitability in the market (Wong & Ngai, 2023). Operational performance is the ability of a firm to supply and manufacture products more efficiently for its end consumers through flexibility, quality, pricing, cost reduction, increased efficiency, and delivery (Zhu et al., 2022). A firm's BDAC results in a positive association with a firm's competitive advantage through an improved operations management process (De Rijck, 2022). Big data analytics management capability is positively and significantly associated with the effects of BDA on the operational performance of a firm (T. Karaboga et al., 2022).

BDA capabilities that include infrastructure, human resources' technical expertise, and management capabilities are strongly related to operational performance (Yasmin et al., 2020). Big data predictive analytics supported with managerial and technical skills have a positive impact on the operational performance of organizations from various industries that include banking, insurance, manufacturing, technology, etc. (Gupta et al., 2020). Data analytics capabilities which encompass tools, processes, techniques, and abilities that enable an organization to process, visualize, analyze, organize, and transform data to provide useful insights, and support decision-making, operational planning, and execution, have direct and significant positive effects on operational performance (Wong & Ngai, 2023). Sensing capabilities that include engaging in information processing activities such as evaluating, filtering,

interpreting, and scanning information, developing or identifying opportunities (e.g., technological), and generating market intelligence, learning from the market environment, and taking actions based on acquired knowledge, have a direct positive effect on operational performance (Wong & Ngai, 2023).

Big data analytics powered by artificial intelligence positively and significantly impact operational performance in manufacturing firms (Dubey et al., 2020). BDAC positively influences the operational performance of banks in Malaysia (Aziz, Long, & Hussain, 2023). Data capabilities positively influence SMEs' operational performance by creating knowledge that builds supply chain capabilities (Hautala-Kankaanpaa, 2023). BDAC positively moderates the impact of green supply chain management efforts on operational performance in retail stores (Shahzad et al., 2022). Big data analytics capabilities have a positive correlation with integration capability, while a higher integration capability results in a higher operational performance in high-tech firms using AI applications in the manufacturing process (C-H. Chen, 2023). A data-driven culture significantly moderates the relationship between analytics capabilities or sensing capabilities and operational performance of MSMEs in the food industry in China (Wong & Ngai, 2023).

Big Data and Innovative Performance (Innovation)

Performance is conceptualized as innovation, which means creating something new or modifying existing products or services. Innovation is the process of optimizing new ideas and integrating knowledge, creativity, and management for value creation and competitiveness (Thuethongchai, Taiphapoon, Chandrachai, & Triukose, 2020). Innovation performance is measured as the number of patents developed or perceived performance of innovation in comparison with competitors, and innovativeness entails product/service newness and meaningfulness (Duan, Cao, & Edwards, 2018). Big data analytics help firms in uncovering insights that are valuable in adapting, reconfiguring, transforming, and changing business processes in creating innovation (Yoshikunia, Dwivedi, Zhou, & Wamba, 2023).

BDA helps firms to acquire a deeper and richer understanding of data about business processes, operations, markets, and competitors, which is valuable in the innovation of products and processes (Yoshikunia et al.,

2023). Big data analytics is necessary in developing service innovation because it enables improvements (design and delivery of service to customers) of service innovation and the development of firms' service capabilities, which are suitable for gaining competitive advantage (Thuethongchai et al., 2020). Data-driven culture moderates the relationship between business analytics and environmental scanning which results in assimilating and exploiting external information for product innovation and competitive advantage (Duan et al., 2018). Incorporating big data analytics in seizing, sensing, and transforming business processes builds organizational capabilities for innovation (Yoshikunia et al., 2023). BDA capabilities are useful in optimizing and adjusting routines, prioritizing and developing new innovative business processes to achieve innovation and leveraging innovations in ways that make an organization competitive in the constantly changing business environment (Yoshikunia et al., 2023).

Big Data and Environmental Performance

Environmental performance is a type of performance that consists of efforts to reduce solid waste, air emissions, effluent waste, and hazardous material use, and increased sustainable distribution (Zhu et al., 2022). BDAC positively impacts environmental performance in manufacturing firms (Zhu et al., 2022). BDAC positively moderates the impact of green supply chain management efforts on environmental performance (Shahzad et al., 2022). Big data and predictive analytics adoption have a positive and significant relationship with environmental performance in the food waste and recycling industry (Nilashi et al., 2023). Big data analytics cum artificial intelligence-enabled decisions have positive effects on green supply chain collaboration and green supply chain collaboration positively impacts environmental performance in healthcare facilities (Benzidia, Makaoui, & Bentahar, 2020). The assimilation of big data through acceptance and routinization positively impacts green supply chain management practices and consequently environmental performance (Q. Ali, Salman, Yaacob, Zaini, & Abdullah, 2020). BDAC significantly impacts environmental performance which includes waste minimization, energy efficiency, utilization of sustainable materials, efficient use or reuse or reduction of resources, and compliance with environmental regulations over a long duration (Sahoo, Upadhyay, & Kumar, 2023).

Big Data and Supply Chain Performance

Supply chain performance is measured in terms of order fill rate, on-time delivery, and inventory turnover (Cheng & Lu, 2018). Big data analytics have a positive impact on supply chain agility, i.e., responding to sudden and unexpected changes in the market in the auto components industry (Dubey, Gunasekaran, & Childe, 2018). The use of big data analytics is positively related to supply chain adaptability (i.e., produces a 59.8% variance in adaptability), while adaptability triggers significant positive effects on supply chain performance. Supply chain adaptability involves the capacity to re-configure resources to adapt to changes in market supply and demand and a competitive environment (Cheng & Lu, 2018). The utilization of big data analytics positively impacts supply chain performance by creating business growth in U.S. companies (D. Q. Chen et al., 2015). The use of big data analytics is positively related to efficiency and explains a 43.5% variance in the efficiency of fashion manufacturing firms' omni-channel to retailers that include reducing inventory, cycle time, and defective products, while efficiency of the omni-channel generates significant positive effects on supply chain performance (Cheng & Lu, 2018). Data-driven supply chains have a significant positive effect on four dimensions of supply chain capabilities which are information exchange, coordination, activity integration, and responsiveness in the manufacturing industry in China (Yu, Chavez, Jacobs, & Feng, 2018). AI-driven big data analytics culture positively impacts humanitarian supply chain agility (responding quickly and cost-effectively to changes or highly unpredictable crises in the shortest possible time) and humanitarian supply chain resilience (coping with disruptions and returning to normalcy or the degree of change that a supply chain network can accommodate while retaining the same control on structure and function) which ultimately help enhance humanitarian supply chain performance (Dubey et al., 2022). BDAC mediates the connection between environmental performance and sustainable supply chain management practices that take into account environmental, economic, and social sustainable development when managing material and information flows and enterprise interactions along the supply chain (Zhu et al., 2022).

Big Data and Competitive Performance

Competitive performance is the extent to which an organization achieves its objectives in comparison with its major competitors (Mikalef et al., 2020). Competitive performance is the economic value of outperforming competitors, which includes growth performance (corporate growth), financial performance, current market share, etc. (Huang, Song, Xie, Li, & He, 2022; Song et al., 2022). BDAC enhances competitive performance (growth and financial performance) through the mediating effects of business model attributes such as infrastructure and value (Song et al., 2022).

Big data and predictive analytics capabilities increase an organization's competitive advantage by improving its environmental and economic performance (Nilashi et al., 2023). Big data analytics capabilities help in sensing the environment, differentiating organizations from competitors, creating value for customers, and spawning competitive advantages (Hautala-Kankaanpaa, 2023). BDAC has a significant and positive effect on the realization of a competitive advantage (De Rijck, 2022). Big data analytics positively impact an organization's competitive advantage (Dubey et al., 2018; Oesterreich et al., 2022). BDA contributes to the generation of valuable and hard-to-imitate knowledge resources, e.g., the understanding of past and present trends and prediction of future trends, which, concurrently, lead to the development of sustainable competitive advantage (Awan et al., 2021).

Big data analytics capabilities influence dynamic capabilities (the capacity to sense, seize, and shape either opportunities or threats to achieve or maintain competitiveness) and consequently enhance operational capabilities, which help organizations in building competitive performance (Mikalef et al., 2020). BDA technology capabilities (the capacity to guarantee data acquisition and development) and BDA management capabilities (the capacity to integrate core business operational functions), have strong and positive associations with resource bricolage, while resource bricolage is positively associated with competitive performance (Huang et al., 2022). BDA management capabilities are positively associated with resource optimization, i.e., efficient coordination and allocation of standardized high-quality resources toward

reaching specific goals and demands, and resource optimization further leads to competitive performance (Huang et al., 2022).

Big Data and Market Performance

Marketing performance is a type of performance that is linked to organizational competitiveness. Marketing performance is a firm's ability to understand and meet customers' needs better than the competition through pricing, product development, channel management, marketing communications, etc. (Suoniemi et al., 2017). BDA system quality and BDA information quality that encompasses accuracy, format, currency, and completeness are important in enhancing business value and market performance (Ji-fan Ren et al., 2016). BDA capabilities that include data, technology, basic resources, technical skills, managerial skills, data-driven culture, and organizational learning, positively influence the marketing performance of firms in the Malaysian banking sector (Aziz et al., 2023). BDA-enabled sensing capability (sensing capability is the organization's ability to explore the market and develop opportunities) has a significant positive influence on market performance (Fosso Wamba et al., 2020). BDAC accounts for an 11.08% increase in market share (Yasmin et al., 2020). Big data predictive analytics capabilities that entail managerial and technical skills positively influence the market performance of various firms (Gupta et al., 2020). Organizations' analytics culture (analytics culture refers to the organization's practices and behavior patterns about analytics) has a significant positive influence on market performance (Fosso Wamba et al., 2020). The association of big data analytics with entrepreneurial orientation when positively moderated by environmental dynamism such as turbulence or stability enhances marketing performance (Dubey et al., 2020).

The Contextual Factors Intervening in the Big Data-Performance Connection

All organizations do not employ the same approach when deploying big data analytics to support their business strategies and how big data analytics is leveraged towards value creation differs according to contexts (Mikalef et al., 2019). For example, a critical element such as organizational readiness (preparedness, desire, and competence) support BDA adoption/implementation that is associated with

improving company effectiveness or business performance (Lutfi et al., 2022). A key contextual factors that determines the outcomes of big data in influencing a firm's performance is resistance to change or inertia (the tendency of stakeholders to return to their previous ways of making decisions) at multiple levels within the organization when attempting to implement data-driven decision-making (Mikalef et al., 2019).

An organization's analytics culture has a significant positive moderating effect on BDA-enabled sensing capability and customer linking capability's relationships with strategic business value, financial performance, and market performance (Fosso Wamba et al., 2020). The big data analytics strategy (that includes a clear sense of direction or roadmap about how big data analytics can improve business and a top-down strategy) is a significant factor that contributes to attaining performance gains (Mikalef et al., 2019) and analytics capability–business strategy alignment moderates the relationship between BDAC and financial performance (Akter, 2016).

A blend of resources under various contexts in the application of big data may lead to improvements in performance. Differences in resource importance according to organizational context in the application of big data have significant effects on performance outcomes and different combinations of resources contribute significantly to firms' performance depending on the size of the firm and other characteristics of the external environment (Mikalef et al., 2019). Resource commitment, which is the allocation of resources such as time, money, and personnel for achieving specific strategic goals and objectives, positively moderates the relationship between BDAC and environmental performance (Sahoo et al., 2023).

Knowledge management practices, i.e., the systematic process of acquiring, converting, evaluating, retrieving, and sharing the knowledge resources for improving organizational performance, partially mediate the relationship between BDA applications and organizational performance in SMEs (Shabbir & Gardezi, 2020). Sharing of information, e.g., target market data, concerns, internal changes, proprietary information, and core business processes in the hospitality industry helps in developing efforts toward the implementation of BDA and in improving the effectiveness of BDA implementation and business performance (Lutfi et al., 2022).

Employing a combination of privacy and ethics frameworks and compliance-based data governance frameworks helps in successfully using data in gaining a competitive advantage in the tourism and hospitality organizations (Yallop & Seraphin, 2020). Ethics and legislation are significant contexts when conducting big data analytics that create business values, e.g., GDPR may pose a threat or an opportunity depending on how the big data from social media is analyzed in cases where users need to be profiled (Mikalef et al., 2019).

Figure 1: The Big Data-Performance Connection

Discussion

Theoretical Implications

This study contributes to knowledge by presenting the big data-performance connection model, propositions, and theory, which explain how performance is generated in the era of big data. The constructs of the model originate from findings from literature about how big data leads to performance. This article underpins the path through which big data builds and improves performance. Based on the findings from

literature, this article presents a theoretical statement that provides a coherent description of how big data leads to performance. *The big data-performance connection posits that performance is a function of the BDAC that encompasses knowledge, skills (managerial, business, & technical), sensing, seizing, transformation, and tangible and intangible resources integrated into big data analytics for the generation of insights from big data under varying conditions (environment) or contexts, which can be incorporated into decision-making that engenders competitive advantage.* The interrelationships between the constructs of the big data-performance connection model are herewith described. Performance is an outcome and is a product of many variables. The variables include big data, big data analytics, big data analytics capabilities, insights, and decision making, and competitive advantage. Performance is described as a function because a function in mathematics is a procedure that relates or transforms one number, quantity, or entity to another based on defined rules. For example, if $y = 2x + 1$, then y is a function of x , i.e., $y = f(x)$, whereby y is the dependent variable and x is the independent variable (APA, 2018). Performance is a dependent variable that involves independent variables that include big data analytics capabilities, big data analytics, big data, and unique organizational and environmental factors or contexts which are interacting to produce valuable insights that are useful in supporting decision-making.

According to Jarmon (2023), a function is a specific type of relation between a set of inputs or domains and corresponding outputs or codomains. Thus, this article presents the assumption that *performance is a relationship that occurs in varying contexts between big data, big data analytics (BDA), and big data analytics capabilities (BDAC) for collecting, storing, analyzing, and utilizing big data sets in generating knowledge or insights for enhancing decision-making.*

Specifically, the level of knowledge, level of skills, the capacity for seizing, sensing, and transforming play a crucial role in the collection, storage, analysis, and utilization of big data in generating insights for enhancing decision-making. The inputs under varying contexts are big data, big data analytics, big data analytics capabilities and the outputs or the codomains are insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage. There is a many-to-one relationship among the variables. The many-to-one relationships under

varying contexts involve big data, big data analytics, big data analytics capabilities, and performance. Whereby, the inputs are differing levels of big data, big data analytics, big data analytics capabilities, and unique contexts and the outputs or codomains are insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage. Depending on organizational or environmental factors, big data and the implementation of big data analytics, which is dependent on the capabilities for big data analytics such as level of knowledge, level of skills, sensing, seizing, and transforming, in conjunction with the intangible resources and tangible resources described in BDAC framework, lead to the generation of outputs such as valuable insights, decisions, and competitive advantage. Figure one portrays the big data-performance connection.

The conceptual reasoning behind the big data-performance connection model is based on the assumption that the association between big data, big data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities is crucial in building performance. For instance, big data is regarded as a form of capital that enlarges organizational responsiveness and informed decision-making, which influences strategic and operational processes and ultimately paves the way for new competitive advantage and improved organizational performance (Oesterreich et al., 2022). Firms that apply big data applications for competitive intelligence, business intelligence, and customer interface have higher performance effects (Bughin, 2016). For performance to occur, be it improved or increased performance in the desired domains, the interactions between big data, big data analytics, and big data capabilities must result in valuable and actionable insights or knowledge, and enhanced or improved decision-making. Big data analytics algorithms help in generating valuable insights and decisions that reduce risks (Gul & Al-Faryan, 2023). Data-driven decision-making culture enables the generation of insights in enhancing business performance (Gul & Al-Faryan, 2023). Firms that utilized BDA had improved decision making in manufacturing operations, which resulted in added benefits for the firms and their customers (Popovic et al., 2016). BDA is important in promoting real-time decision-making, fact-based and proactive actions, and value proposition enhancements (Popovic et al., 2016). Moreover, some contexts intervene and regulate the relationships between big data, big data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities in building performance. Some of the elements that influence big data, big

data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities roles in impacting performance are decision-making process, organizational readiness, resistance to change, resource optimization, knowledge management processes, and ethics. Mikalef et al. (2019, p. 269) indicated that different combinations of big data analytics resources play a greater or lesser importance depending on the contexts of application and the conditions that characterize them. This study established that there are various domains of performance associated with the input and output processes involving big data, big data analytics, big data analytics capabilities, insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage. The types of performance include organizational, environmental, competitive, market, operational, supply chain, etc. This article presents some if-then conjectures in providing directions about the big data-performance connection theory and in underpinning the conceptual model.

Proposition 1: If changes in big data, big data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities are positively associated with insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage, then performance will improve as a result of changes in insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage.

Proposition 2: If changes in the level of knowledge, level of skills, and capacity for sensing, seizing, and transforming encompassed in big data analytics capabilities are positively associated with big data analytics, then performance will improve as a result of changes in insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage.

Proposition 3: If changes in big data, big data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities operating within some contexts are positively associated with insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage, then performance will improve as a result of changes in insights, decision-making, and competitive advantage under beneficial contexts.

Implications for Practice

As the business environment is characterized by constant changes and diversity of players in various economic sectors, the survival and sustainability of firms depend on their quality of functioning, the success

of their processes, and how well tasks, functions, strategies, goals, etc., are executed in comparison with other firms in the industry. A firm's quality of performance is a critical factor that determines its survival, growth, and competitiveness in a constantly evolving technological and business landscape. A firm's ability to draw performance gains from big data is essential for its continued existence in a highly competitive business environment. In the era of big data, performance gains does not depend only or just on the adoption of big data but on the use of big data analytics that promote the development of valuable insights which support informed data-driven decision-making that enables an organization to develop competitive advantage. Moreover, big data analytics capabilities are essential in the achievement of goals and objectives, and for the effective functioning of organizations.

The approach through which firms can translate their big data into performance is by having personnel with the capabilities to analyze data amongst other resources. This requires developing the workers' big data analytics capabilities required for analyzing data, extracting insights, and appropriating value from data. C-H. Chen (2023) argued that BDA capabilities support organizations in integrating and analyzing data toward realigning business processes in a continuously changing environment. As human resource play a crucial role in realizing the benefits from big data, it is pertinent for executives to deploy methods of increasing stakeholders' level of knowledge, level of skills, and building employees' capacity for sensing, seizing, and transforming through on-going feedback and developmental activities. According to Yasmin et al. (2020), big data analytics lead to improved performance under conditions of adequate technological capabilities and other firm-specific practices such as organizational learning, experimentation, etc., To derive performance-improving benefits from big data investments and implementation of big data analytics, firms must build big data analytics capabilities. For example, firms need to develop unique information processing skills necessary for big data analytics and fulfil technological, technical, human capital requirements, etc., that are essential for the successful implementation of big data analytics, that would enable organizational value creation processes and improve a company's competitive advantage (Arshad et al., 2022).

In addition, firms' investment in key processes and practices will enable the derivation of value from big data investments (Mikalef et al., 2019). For instance, employing the right analytic tools for the big data analytic processes while ensuring the analysis generate valuable insights that can be incorporated into a firm's decision-making process is valuable for improving performance. Osuszek et al. (2016) indicates that access to accurate and up-to-date trusted information, as well as the analytical tools to make sense of the information are beneficial for informed decision-making, more consistent outcomes, and the overall company's business. The integration of activities, tools, information exchange, and responsiveness to change in the supply chain management capabilities positively mediate the relationship between big data analytics capabilities and sustainable performance (Riggs, Roldan, Real, & Felipe, 2023). Precisely, big data technology resources, which are novel information technologies necessary in handling big data, e.g., non-relational databases, middleware, data warehousing, and analytic tools, are pertinent to the exploitation of big data in enhancing firm performance (Suoniemi et al., 2017).

Executives can self-assess their readiness for big data implementation and the possible outcomes of their big data investments by evaluating their big data analytics elements. For example, big data analytics that is built on big data management capabilities (e.g., BDA planning, investment, coordination and control), big data technological capabilities (e.g., technological components, applications, software and physical components that determine connectivity, modularity, and compatibility), big data talent capabilities (e.g., technical skills, technology management skills, business skills, and relational skills) have a significant positive relationship with sustainable product development that encompasses environmental (circular economy), and economic (e.g., cost reduction) dimensions, and in turn, sustainable product development significantly and positively impact organizational performance (S. Ali et al., 2020).

Moreover, organizational leaders need to control intervening elements, and regulate the environment or contexts in the big data-to-performance relationships such as culture, ethics, organizational readiness, organizational learning, environmental dynamism, resource commitment, etc., Specifically, firms that would derive enhanced performance from big data and the analytics processes must understand the value

of big data and build organizational readiness/acceptance for big data analytics. Mikalef et al. (2019) indicated that the blend of resources under various contexts in the application of big data lead to improvements in performance.

Future Directions and Conclusions

This article suggests that future research may investigate performance connected to big data, such as market(ing) performance and financial performance, more in-depthly as the literature covering these types of performance is scant. In addition, researchers may devote more attention to how big data analytics generate insights and how insights and decision-making are relevant for enhancing performance. The propositions presented in this article offers the research community some assumptions for further investigations.

In sum, the adoption and implementation of big data, big data analytics, and the building of requisite proficiencies in managing BDA are key to developing various categories of performance. Performance is a relationship between big data, big data analytics, and big data analytics capabilities under various conditions and contexts. Specifically, improved performance will only be achieved if and only if big data is appropriately processed under favorable conditions through big data analytics that generate valuable insights, hard-to-imitate knowledge, informed and enhanced business decision-making, and sustainable competitive advantage.

Essentially, firms with requisite knowledge and skills and the capacity for sensing, seizing, and transforming will be effective in generating useful insights from big data. Human resource play a crucial role in realizing the benefits from big data; especially, the level of knowledge, skills, the ability to sense, seize and transform are significant factors in the big data-performance relationship.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not Applicable

Consent for publication

Not Applicable

Availability of data and materials

The datasets used and analyzed for this current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests

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Authors' Contribution

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Appendix A

The Publication Screening and Selection Process

Figure 2: The Publication Selection Process